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Evaluating the Various Indeterminate germplasm of tomato hybrids for yield components under High Tunnel at Climatic condition of Balochistan

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Abstract

The trial was conducted at Directorate of Vegetable Seed Production, ARI Sariab Quetta-Pakistan. Main aim of this trial was to evaluate the potential of indeterminate tomatoes hybrids under high tunnel. The traditional practices of tomato cultivation are very lethargic and farming communities of specially tomato growers facing many agronomic problems due to such practices i.e. low yield per hectare, fruit quality (size and shape) and other management issues. This study revealed that through indeterminate cultivars/hybrids of tomato the yield per acre increased vividly within existing infrastructure of indigenous agriculture. In this trial 6 cultivars were tested among them Sahil performed well and its yield per hectare was recorded 120.72 tons. All cultivars were shown that indeterminate cultivars/hybrids have five (5) time more yield potential than regular tomato crops. This study recommend the utilization of Indeterminate tomatoes under tunnels through this way farmers will get more yield and improve their socio economic status and contribute healthy Gross domestic Production (GDP) at country level.

Key words (Indeterminate Tomatoes, High Tunnel, Advance Agronomic Practices and Tomato Yield)

1. Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum L*) is one of the most valuable Vegetable crop of Balochistan as well as Pakistan, which was also articulated by Mohammad Sajjad *et al* (2011) [1]. Tomato contain many healthy agents like Minerals such as calcium, potassium, Magnesium and phosphorus along with that ample amount of Vitamins i.e. A, and C which was also alleged by Dutta *et al* [2] which are essential human's health. Genetic make of tomato is constituted as true diploid, having $2n=24$ which was mentioned by Khan, I *et al* (2017) [3]. In Balochistan Tomato grown on an area of 12722 hectare and production on such area is 383690 tons (Government of Balochistan 2014-15) [4]. Tomato grown in both season i.e. Rabi and Kharif in Balochistan. Yield potential of determinate tomatoes are very low as compare to indeterminate tomatoes. The average yield of determinate tomatoes in Balochistan is 7-8 tons per hectare during Kharif season and 12-15 tons per hectare in Rabi season which is far least as compare to adjacent provinces. As compare to determinate tomatoes the yield potential of Indeterminate tomatoes are enormous. Indeterminate tomatoes required special arrangement for their production such as stacking or hanging ropes. For this purposes high tunnels are one of the best structure for the production of quality oriented tomatoes. In perspective of consumers, fruit quality and shape are the main factor to attract for purchase, Amina J. Gojeh *et al* also reported the same in her findings (2012) [5]. In business of vegetables and especially in tomatoes profit depends on high yield and its quality, Martin M. Maboko *et al* (2018) also explained that in tomato, profit directly relay on more yield and tomato quality [6]. More produce means more profit and more profit means prosperity. Under high tunnel conditions farmers not only gain high yield but also the quality of fruit become enhanced due to covered environment. The main aim of this study was convince the farming communities of Balochistan about the potential of tunnel farming regarding tomato crops. Under tunnels farmers can get ten (10) time more yield of tomato as compare to their traditional practices. In results it was unveil that the least performing variety Sandal alone produced 84.04 tons per hectare which is far much

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greater than regular (determinate tomato) tomato production. According to the finding of this experiment cultivation of indeterminate tomatoes are vigorously recommend for the growers of Balochistan to mitigate the issue of low yield per hectare problem in province.

2. Material and Methods

The experiment was conducted at Directorate of Vegetable Seed Production Farm, Agriculture Research Institute (ARI) Sariab Quetta-Balochistan, Pakistan during Kharif Season 2017 and 2018. The experimental site was located on 30.08° N latitude and 66.96° E with the elevation of 1679 meter above MSL. There were six commercial hybrids were included in experiment to evaluate the potential of yield of Indeterminate Tomatoes. Among six hybrids two were from Ayoub Agriculture Research Institute (AARI) Faisalabad-Pakistan which were Sandal and Salar. Sahil-F₁ was product of Syngenta Pakistan, Anna from Seminis Monsanto Pakistan, APCL was product USA and Paipai was product of Enza Pakistan. All these hybrid seeds were purchased commercially from open market except Sandal and Salar which were acquired from AARI-Faisalabad-Pakistan. Experiment was designed on Complete Randomized Design (CRD) with three repeats of each treatments. Hybrids were taken as treatments. Due to tunnel conditions and uniform irrigation system CRD method was applied to collect the data of all parameters. Tomatoes seeds were raised on plastic tray method during 1st week

of February. In this method the germination percentage of seedlings become increase and also easy to manage with other agronomic practices, Pandiayaraja P. *et al* (2017) elucidated in his finding that raising nursery on poly plastic trays decrease the issue of seedling mortality and increase seedling vitality [7]. Seedlings were transplanted in tunnel in last week of March manually. Irrigation was applied through drip irrigation system along with fertigation. Standard fertilizers (N.P.K) were applied homogenously to all treatment. Data of seven parameters were collected, that were number of clusters per plant, number of fruits per cluster, number of picking, plant height (ft), single fruit weight (gm), yield per plant (Kg's) and Yield per hectare⁻¹ (tons). Data of all parameters were highly significant. Data of two years were collectively pooled for statistical analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level probability, as mentioned by Gomez K.A and Gomez A.A [8]. Statistix version 8.1 software was employed to analyze the data accordingly.

3. Results and Discussion

Number of Cluster:

This parameter was one of the signified parameter which influenced the over all yield of tomatoes. Brain A.Mitchell *et al* (2019) also find that clusters in tomato crop influence the yield [9]. Results divulge that, Sahil-F₁ obtained highest numbers of cluster per plant which was 9.8, Anna came on 2nd tier with 8.22 cluster per plant, APCL, Salar and Paipai showed not very significant difference and on last Sandal attain 5.2 cluster. Shaill showed high number of cluster as compare to rest. Data mentioned in Tab-Indi-NoC.

Tab-Indi-NoC

Hybrids	No of Cluster
Sahil	4 9.8889 A
Anna	2 8.2222 B
APCL	3 7.1111 C
Salar	5 6.7778 C
Paipai	6 6.5556 C
Sandal (Control)	1 5.2222 D

No of Fruit Per Cluster:

Number of fruit per cluster also influenced the yield of indeterminate tomatoes on high perspective, the same finding was mentioned by Brain A.Mitchell *et al* (2019) [10]. In indeterminate Tomatoes comes in clusters. The yield directly depends on the number of fruits per cluster. This study reveled that Sahil performed best among rest and achieved 9 fruits per cluster on an average. Ana came on 2nd and attain >

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then 7 fruits. In Salar and Paipai there were no any significant difference and both have > then 5 fruits and in D group. In last there is Sandal which possessed 4.1 fruits on an average. Data mentioned in Tab-Indi-NoF.

Tab-Indi-NoF

Hybrids	No of fruit per cluster
Sahil	9.1111 A
Anna	7.6667 B
APCL	6.6667 C
Salar	5.5556 D
Paipai	5.1111 D
Sandal (Control)	4.1111 E

No of Picking

Picking is integral agronomic practice in Tomato crop either determinate or indeterminate. In this experiment Sahil got more the 11 pickings and Ana on 2nd with more than 10 picking. Among APCL, Salar and Paipai there were no any significant difference and all three ranked in group C. Sandal was the least gaining variety in number of picking under uplands of Balochistan i.e. 6.55.

Hybrids	No of Picking
4Sahil	11.556 A
2Anna	10.444 B
3APCL	9.3333 C
4Salar	8.6667 C
5Paipai	8.6667 C
1Sandal (Control)	6.5556 D

Plant Height (feet)

Indeterminate tomatoes (I.T) are renowned for their height. In normal condition I.T attain up to 10 feet. Results of experiment revealed that Sahil expressed more than 11 feet, Ana on other hand achieved feet of 10.62 feet and become 2nd. APCL, Salar and Paipai were having similar height i.e 9.72, 9.46, and, 9.15 respectively. In last Sandal scored 7.87 feet.

Hybrids	Plant Height (feet)
4Sahil	11.03 A
2Anna	10.62 B
3APCL	9.72 C
4Salar	9.46 CD
5Paipai	9.15 D
1Sandal (Control)	7.87 E

Fruit Weight (gm)

Fruit weight have very significant impact on yield. Results of experiment highly significant. Sahil attain 83.77 grams, Anna achieved 74.73 gm, APCL showed 60.13 gm, Salar, Paipai, and Sandal achieved 54.82, 51.47 and 48.65 gm respectively. Sahil performed best among the rest of hybrids in experiment.

Hybrids	Fruit Weight (gm)
4Sahil	83.778 A
2Anna	74.733 B
3APCL	60.133 C
4Salar	54.822 D
5Paipai	51.478 E
1Sandal (Control)	48.656 F

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Yield Per Plant (Kg's)

Single plant yield poses direct effect on yield of Indeterminate tomatoes. Single plant yield varies from variety to variety. Results of this experiment revealed that Sahil achieved 5.171 Kg per plant which was highest single plant yield. Anna came on 2nd tier and attain 4.60 Kg per plant. APCL and Salar were on same tier which were recorded 4.2 and 4.0 Kg per plant respectively. Paipai was second last performer among all in single plant yield that was 3.5 Kgs. Sandal was the last in entire expression of work and achieved 3.03 Kg.

Hybrids	Yield per Plant (Kg's)
4Sahil	5.1711 A
2Anna	4.6000 B
3APCL	4.2900 C
4Salar	4.0889 C
5Paipai	3.5444 D
1Sandal (Control)	3.0333 E

Yield Per Hectare (Tons)

Low yield production is one of the most demising factor in determinate tomatoes in Balochistan-Pakistan. The yield of indeterminate tomatoes were enormous as compare to determinate tomatoes. Results deduced that Sahil yield highest among all that was 120.72 tons per hectare⁻¹. Anna possessed 102.28 tons per hectare. APCL Salar and Paipai achieved 99.76, 94.90 and 90.13 tons per hectare respectively. Sandal stood on last with 84.04 tons per hectare. All results were highly significant.

Hybrids	Yield Per Hec (Tons)
4Sahil	120.72 A
2Anna	102.28 B
3APCL	99.767 C
4Salar	94.900 D
5Paipai	90.133 E
1Sandal (Control)	84.044 F

Conclusion

Results of experiment inferred that indeterminate tomatoes were best in term of high yield and fruit quality. Data of all parameters revealed that, Sahil (hybrid) performed well in entire experiment. The yield potential of Sahil was humongous as compare to determinate tomatoes. Farmers of Balochistan are combating with the stigma of low yield per hectare. If farmers adopt tunnel farming they can get more yield from same piece of land from where they getting low yield in current scenario. Also through adopting tunnel farming and indeterminate tomatoes farmers of province will able to get off season tomatoes which not only increase the yield capacity but also improve their socio-economic condition rigorously. The technology of Tunnel farming for the farmers of Balochistan are immense in current situation and play a pivotal role in GDP of overall country.

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